

UTILIZATION OF CHITOSAN WASTE CRAB SHELLS (*PORTUNUS PELAGICUS*) AS CORROSION INHIBITORS IN SOFT STEEL IN PEAT WATER MEDIA WITH ELECTROPLATING METHOD

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Abstract

Corrosion is a common problem in the use of metal-based materials. Corrosion rates are accelerated when metal materials experience direct contact with corrosive compounds such as peat water. Peat soils have poor physical properties for construction and metal materials. West Kalimantan itself has a pH of 3-5, where peat water is very acidic and very corrosive. As time goes by the construction material will experience corrosion. Corrosion can cause an increase in maintenance costs incurred and waste of mineral resources. Various attempts have been made to protect metals from corrosion, including electroplating which is a cathode protection mechanism, and the use of inhibitors as corrosion coatings. This study aims to determine the effectiveness of corrosion inhibitors of chitosan waste of crab shell (*Portunus pelagicus*) in soft steel in peat water media by electroplating method. Specimens used are soft steel. The electroplating process was carried out in an electrolyte solution containing 10% chitosan inhibitor (*Portunus pelagicus*) waste concentration of 10% for 3 hours electroplating at a voltage of 20 volts. Metal immersion in pH 5 water for 1, 3 and 5 days. Chitosan testing was carried out by FTIR analysis, while corrosion rate testing was carried out by calculation method. The results showed that chitosan obtained had 85.31% deacetylation degree. The results of soaking peat water in a row at 1, 3 and 5 days with pH of peat water 5, ie 0.0045 gr / cm².jam, 0.0056 gr / cm².jam, 0.0089 gr / cm².hour. For the results of the inhibition efficiency value was 63.52%.

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1. Introduction

Indonesia is one of the countries that has the largest peatland area in the world, which is 10.8% of Indonesia's land area (Anggriawan *et al.*, 2015). Peatland in Indonesia reaches 14.9 million ha or 7.8% of the total area of Indonesia 191.09 million ha. Peatlands in Indonesia are mainly found in Sumatra, Kalimantan and Papua. Kalimantan alone has an area of peatland reaching 4.7 million ha or 32.1% of the area of peat in Indonesia. West Kalimantan is ranked first with an area of 1,680,134 ha or 73.8% of the area of peat in West Kalimantan (Ritung *et al.*, 2011).

West Kalimantan's buildings and construction on average pass through peat soils, while peat soils have poor physical properties for construction purposes, whether for building foundations, underground pipelines, or for storage tanks. As time goes by the construction material will experience corrosion. Corrosion can cause an increase in maintenance costs incurred and waste of mineral resources. Until now, scientists have conducted various studies on corrosion protection methods, but the existing method is still relatively expensive, so it requires a solution to overcome the problem.

Some ways that can slow down the rate of corrosion reactions include the addition of certain substances that function as corrosion reaction inhibitors (Surdia, 1979). In previous studies, there were various kinds of inhibitors used, one of which was a chitosan inhibitor. According to Maria et al's research, (2011) chitosan can be used as a corrosion inhibitor in steel in peat water. The optimum conditions of chitosan occur at pH 3, coating inhibition technique and interaction time for 3 days is 88.73%, while chitosan (2) occurs in pH 6, dyeing inhibition technique and interaction time for 3 days is 93.32%. However, in this study the method used was less optimal so that it could cause corrosion coating to not last long and the possibility of coating did not last long.

Therefore, this research needs to be done to increase knowledge about the use of chitosan from crab shell waste (*Portunus pelagicus*) as a corrosion inhibitor in soft steel in peat water media and use the development of different methods, namely electroplating methods to determine the maximum results of corrosion coating techniques.

2. Method Of Research

2.1 Time and Place of Research Implementation

This research was conducted for approximately 3 months, starting from April 2018 - June 2018. The electroplating process was carried out at the UNTAN Chemical Engineering Laboratory. The peat water used in this study came from the Serdam Kubu Raya area, West Kalimantan. Indonesia. Characterization using FTIR instruments was carried out at the Chemical Laboratory of FMIPA UGM, Yogyakarta.

2.2 Tools and Materials

The tools needed in this research are Power Supply (BK-Precision DC), Pt electrode, and magnetic stirrer. The photoelectrochemical reactor system consists of UV lamps. Analysis equipment consists of FTIR. In addition, a set of glassware and other laboratory supports such as analytic balance, oven and desiccator. While the materials used are titanium plate, platinum wire, crab shell waste (*Portunus pelagicus*), NaOH (Merck), HCl (Merck), glycerol 98% pa (Merck), distilled water, peat water, ethanol pa (Merck), abrasive paper, acetone pa (Merck), sodium format (HCOONa) (Merck) 0.05 M.

2.3 Research Procedures

2.3.1 Sample preparation

Samples of crab shell waste (*Portunus pelagicus*) were demineralized using HCl solution. The next step is neutralized using NaOH, then the deacetylation stage by heating the shell in 50% NaOH solution at 110°C for 5 hours. The chitosan obtained was analyzed and validated using an IR spectrophotometer.

2.3.2 Testing with Peat Water Media

Soft steel is soaked in peat water media. Measurement of the lost weight of soft steel plate specimens was weighed and then soaked in 10 mL of peat water without and with chitosan with pH of peat water 5, soaking time 1, 3 and 5 days. Then the specimen is weighed again.

2.3.3 Electroplating method

Electroplating is a way of coating the surface of the substrate that takes place in an electrolyte solution. The substrate functions as a cathode while the anode is a source that will later function as a coating material for the substrate. Unidirectional electric current (DC) is channeled to the anode and cathode. The coating is expected to be able to withstand the rate of mobility of dislocations on the surface of the material, so that it will strengthen the nature of the hardness, and corrosion resistance. The advantages of electroplating techniques include electroplating at

room temperature so that it does not cause distortion or structural changes to the substrate (Mulyaningsih et al., 2012).

Electroplating method is carried out by preparing 2 electrodes, titanium plate on anode cell and Pt wire on the cathode cell connected to the Power Supply. Both electrodes were dipped in glycerol solution containing 10% chitosan concentration and 25% water. Anodizing process produces hydrogen gas bubbles around Pt wire at a voltage of 20V DC and accompanied by stirring using a magnetic stirrer for 3 hours.

Anticorrosive tests were carried out on a photoelectrochemical reactor system consisting of 2 compartments namely anode cells and corrosion cells (cathode cells) equipped with UV light sources. At first the surface and metal side were sanded to gloss. Then the dimensions and initial mass of the metal are measured. Then the metal is bound and washed with acetone. After that it is dried and the metal is ready for electroplating. The results of the research changes from the specimen can be seen by measuring the corrosion rate, so that the inhibition efficiency is known. Corrosion rate measurement can use the following formula:

$$\text{Corrosion Rate} = \frac{K.W}{D.A.t} \quad (1)$$

Where:

K= Konstant (mmpy $8,76 \times 10^6$)

W= Weight Loss (gram)

D= Metal Density (gr/cm^3)

A= Surface Area (cm^2)

t= Time

(ASTM D96, 2007)

$$\text{Efisiensi inhibisi} = \frac{V_{ko} - V_{ki}}{V_{ki}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Where, V_{ko} = reaction rate without inhibitors

V_{ki} = the rate of reaction with an inhibitor

3. Specific Results And Potential

3.1 Results Achieved

Making Chitosan and Its Characterization. In this study, used crab shell waste (*Portunus pelagicus*) as an inhibitor for soft steel in peat water media. The procedure for synthesis of chitosan waste from crab shells (*Portunus pelagicus*) is based on research that has been carried out. To determine the degree of deacetylation a line method is used by Moore and Robert, as shown in the following equation:

$$\left[1 - \left(\frac{A_{1588}}{A_{3410}} \times \frac{1}{1.33} \right) \right] \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

Note:

A = $\log(P_0/P)$ = absorbance

A_{1588} = absorbance at the wave board 1588cm^{-1} for cluster absorption amide/acetamide (CH_3CONH)

A_{3410} = absorbance at a wavelength 3410cm^{-1} for hydroxyl group absorption (OH^-).

Based on the above equation, the chitosan from crab shell (*Portunus pelagicus*) waste obtained from this study has a deacetylation degree value of 85.31%. The figure below shows

Figure 1. Chitosan FTIR spectrum waste of crab shell (*Portunus pelagicus*) (Experimental results)

3.2 Testing of Peat Water Media

Peat water used as a medium has a pH of 5 according to the pH conditions of West Kalimantan's peat water with a soaking time of 3 days.

Figure 2. Soft steel before and after corrosion (a) before (b) after soaking peat water (Experimental results)

In the process of corrosion in the soft steel studied, the soaked steel will experience penetration or diffusion from the mother's solution of corrosive peat media. This can affect the value of the resistance that is owned by soft steel when flowed through the current and the O₂ content in the solution has a role in the oxidation process against soft steel so that corrosion occurs. It can be seen from Figure 4.2 that the soft steel specimens have undergone changes due to corrosion.

3.3 Determination and Test of Corrosion Rate

The corrosion process takes place spontaneously and cannot be prevented, but can only be inhibited so that the corrosion process occurs as small as possible. In this study, the corrosion process of soft steel was inhibited in peat water media using chitosan inhibitor of crab shell (*Portunus pelagicus*) waste. While the corrosive environment uses peat water pH 5. The corrosion rate testing is based on the weight reduction that occurs in the material when dipped in the media. The addition of a solution of inhibitor of chitosan shell waste (*Portunus pelagicus*) in peat water solution as a corrosive medium was carried out with a concentration of 10%. After the test object is soaked, the taking is done 3 times, namely on the 3rd days. Substrate which has been coated with chitosan inhibitor of crab shell (*Portunus pelagicus*) was tested for corrosion resistance. The test was carried out using the method using equation (1) according to ASTM D96. The sample was weighed by the initial mass and measured in dimensions (length, width, and finally weighed to calculate the mass lost during the corrosion process.

Table 1. Results of measurement of soft steel soaking peat water without and with electroplating pH 5

Measurement	Thickness (cm)	Length (cm)	Weight (cm)	
Soft steel with soaking peat water without electroplating	before	0,396	6,67	3,94
	after	0,3	6,55	3,95
Soft steel with peat water soaking and by electroplating	before	0,3	6,67	3,93
	after	0,3	6,54	3,96

Based on the table data above it can be seen that soft steel with soaking peat water without electroplating treatment has a smaller dimension and mass difference compared to those given electroplating treatment. This is due to the corrosion effect produced by peat water has a greater impact on soft steel without electroplating treatment. So there is a reduction in the mass of soft steel. This quantitatively the electroplating process carried out using chitosan waste of crab shell (*Portunus pelagicus*) has a positive impact on the success of the prevention of corrosion events in soft steel. The inhibitory efficiency obtained was 63.52% with the concentration of chitosan waste of crabaceous waste at 10%.

3.4 Mechanism of Chitosan Inhibitor of Crab Shell Waste (*Portunus pelagicus*)

This chitosan compound has several functional groups that can interact with soft steel atoms to form a protective layer on the soft steel surface. The group owned by chitosan is NH₂- and OH-groups which can form complexes with metals from their PEB.

Figure 3. Structure of chitosan

Chitosan inhibitor of crab shell (*Portunus pelagicus*) waste in peat water undergoes protonation on functional groups which play an important role in inhibiting corrosion in soft steel. This protonated chitosan molecule chitosan shell (*Portunus pelagicus*) then competes with hydrogen ions (H⁺) to be adsorbed on the cathodic site on the metal surface so that the formation of Hydrogen (H₂) gas becomes reduced. Chloride ion (Cl⁻) in the medium of peat water reacts with positively charged metal parts on the soft steel surface and makes other negative ions gather in the interface between the electrodes and corrosive media, so that the chitosan molecule waste of the crab shell (*Portunus pelagicus*) becomes easy to adsorbed on anodic soft steel site. Mechanism of protonated adsorption of chitosan crabs (*Portunus pelagicus*) on soft steel surfaces is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The effect of concentration on anodic inhibitors on corrosion rates (Trethewey, 1991)

Neutral molecules are adsorbed by soft steel with a mechanism to replace water molecules on the soft steel surface.

4. Conclusion

From this study it can be concluded that:

1. Chitosan material of crab shell waste (*Portunus pelagicus*) is an alternative material that is safe, easy to obtain, cheap, and environmentally friendly and effective in preventing corrosion using electroplating methods on soft steel. Especially for systems that are in direct contact with liquid corrosive.
2. Chitosan obtained from crab shell waste (*Portunus pelagicus*) has a deacetylation degree of 85.31%.
3. The corrosion rate of soft steel without the addition of chitosan inhibitor of crab shell (*Portunus pelagicus*) on corrosive media of peat water at 1, 3, and 5 days soaking has increased that is 0.0045 gr / cm-1, 0.0056 gr / cm -1, 0.0089 gr / cm-1. Whereas the reaction rate of soft steel with the addition of chitosan inhibitor of crab shells (*Portunus pelagicus*) on corrosive media of peat water at 1, 3, and 5 days soaking decreased by 0.004 gr / cm-1, 0.0045 gr / cm-1, 0.004 gr / cm-1.
4. Chitosan of crab shell waste (*Portunus pelagicus*) has the potential as a corrosion inhibitor of soft steel in pH 5 peat water medium with a concentration of 10% and an efficiency value of 63.52%.

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